

Background and scope

- CRC 1411: Rigorous design of particulate products
- Synthesis, separation, classification, simulation and optimization
- 21 research projects with diverse backgrounds:
 - e.g., chemistry, process engineering, mathematics, physics
- Interdisciplinarity of projects reflected in variety of (meta)data:
 - electron tomography, UV-Vis spectra, size distributions, simulation data

UV-Vis spectra

General part of file header

```

1 # name of sample: text
2 # date of measurement: yyyy-mm-dd hh:mm:ss
3 # measuring device: text
  or
4 # simulation parameter file: text
5 # number of measurements averaged: number
6 # baseline type: text
7 # number of wavelength samples (x-data): number

```

Specification for extinction data

```

7 # wavelength in nm measured quantity and unit
8 x-data y-data

```

```

# name of sample : Au_seeds_citrat_diluted_water
# date of measurement : 2025-06-17 12:00:00
# measuring device: Specord 200 Analytik Jena
# number of measurements averaged: 1
# baseline type: water
# number of wavelength samples (x-data): 551
# x-data: wavelength in nm, y-data: extinction / -
+2.500000e+02 +3.918000e-01
+2.510000e+02 +3.875000e-01
+2.520000e+02 +3.847000e-01
+2.530000e+02 +3.821000e-01
+2.540000e+02 +3.790000e-01
+2.550000e+02 +3.773000e-01
+2.560000e+02 +3.747000e-01

```


Full format description

Challenges and objective

- Variety of proprietary formats of raw data from measuring instruments
 - Lack of standardized formats for interdisciplinary (meta)data exchange
- Goal:** Development of standardized data formats for (meta)data exchange of UV-Vis spectra and size distributions
- Long-time:** Initiate community-wide discussion and feedback
- Short-time:** Tailored solution facilitating collaborations and data publications within CRC 1411

Convention

- ASCII code (human readable)
- File extension `.uvvis`
- Comment line starts with `#`
- Dot as decimal separator
- x-data: wavelength in nm
- Information on baseline as comment
- Store average over multiple measurements

Specification for reflectance data

```

7 # number of angle samples (y-data): number
8 # wavelength in nm vs. angle in degrees
9 # z-data: measured quantity and unit
10 y-data
11 x-data z-data for each angle sample

```

```

# Name of sample: AM 03.01.007
# date of measurement: 2025-04-25
# name of measuring device: Cary 7000 with UMA device
# number of measurements averaged: 1 (one measurement with +/- angle)
# baseline type: 100 percent baseline by 0° light source, 180° detector
# number of wavelength samples: 3648
# number of angle samples (y-data): 38
# wavelength in nm vs. measurement angles (60° to -60° in 3° steps)
# z-data : reflectance at certain angle, standard deviation

```

	60	57	54	51	48	45
345	3.93 0.2	-0.0694 0.2	-0.319 0.2	0.556 0.2	0.639 0.2	-0.611 0.2
345	3.93 0.2	-0.0694 0.2	-0.319 0.2	0.556 0.2	0.639 0.2	-0.611 0.2
346	1.04 0.2	0.777 0.2	1.06 0.2	0.934 0.2	0.986 0.2	0.786 0.2
346	1.01 0.2	1.73 0.2	-0.927 0.2	-0.0521 0.2	-2.33 0.2	1.95 0.2
346	0.67 0.2	2.44 0.2	1.98 0.2	3.62 0.2	4.21 0.2	2.73 0.2
346	1.21 0.2	1.3 0.2	1.79 0.2	0.126 0.2	0.961 0.2	0.969 0.2
347	0.176 0.2	0.0367 0.2	0.118 0.2	0.367 0.2	0.0772 0.2	0.181 0.2

Particle/pore size distributions

Format description

```

1 # name of sample: text
2 # date of measurement: yyyy-mm-dd hh:mm:ss
3 # analysis method: text
4 # measuring device: text
  or
5 # simulation parameter file: text
6 # assumption on particle/pore geometry: text
7 # measured length: text
8 # measured part of particle: text
  or
9 # sample mass (pores): number
10 # type of distribution: text
11 # number of bins (x-data): number
12 # unit of x-data: m
13 # unit of y-data: unit
14 # bin particle count
  or
15 pore size pore volume
16 x-data y-data
17 ...

```

Convention

- ASCII code (human readable)
- File extension `.psd`
- Comment line starts with `#`
- Dot as decimal separator
- Distribution type: number count, length, area, volume, intensity, etc.

Full format description

Example for particle size distribution data

```

# name of sample: id42
# date of measurement: 2025/05/13 00:00:00
# analysis method: Godunov simulation
# measuring device or simulation parameter file: /path/to/file.m
# assumption on particle geometry: sphere
# measured length: diameter
# measured part of particle: core and shell
# type of distribution: q0
# number of bins (x-data): 4
# unit of x-data: m
# unit of y-data: -
# bin particle count
1.230000e-04 1.230000e+02
2.345679e-04 4.560000e+02
4.000000e-04 7.890000e+02
1.150000e-03 1.011000e+03

```

Example for pore size distribution data

```

# name of sample: 2022_04_01_KIT-6-35-140_48H_s1_CS_Ar_87K_d3_st2_m2.qps
# date of measurement: 2022-04-01 00:00:00
# analysis method: gas adsorption
# Measuring device: AutoSorb
# assumption on pore geometry: cylindrical
# measured length: diameter
# sample mass: 1.558e-04 kg
# type of distribution: -
# number of bins (x-data): 141
# unit of x-data: m
# unit of y-data: m3/m/kg
# pore size pore volume
4.3300e-10 0.0000e+00
4.6200e-10 0.0000e+00
4.9200e-10 0.0000e+00
5.2200e-10 0.0000e+00

```